

Physical vacuum as a dilatant fluid yields exact solutions to Pioneer anomaly and Mercury's perihelion precession

Marco Fedi,^{1*}

¹Ministero dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca, Rome, Italy

*E-mail: marco.fedi@istruzione.it

Abstract

By using the Lorentz factor as a viscosity term in Stokes's law for objects traveling in a vacuum, Mercury's perihelion precession and the Pioneer anomaly are directly and exactly solved, demonstrating that physical vacuum is a shear-thickening (dilatant) fluid. The modified Stokes's equation also correctly indicates that planetary orbits are stable (over trillions of years). This unexpected feature of physical vacuum may help in achieving quantum relativity and implies interesting consequences for various fields of modern physics.

Keywords: dilatant vacuum, vacuum hydrodynamics, Pioneer anomaly, perihelion precession, general relativity

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1 Introduction

Some authors considered the possibility that the physical vacuum may be a superfluid, a special Bose-Einstein condensate [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. Here, by exactly solving two known anomalies, along with other correct results, it is demonstrated that the physical vacuum rather behaves as a dilatant fluid, as shear stress increases. Sect. 2 introduces a modified Stokes's formula for motion in a shear-thickening vacuum. In Sect. 3, by applying this formula, the Pioneer anomaly, the orbital stability of the planets and Mercury's perihelion precession

are correctly calculated. The Pioneer anomaly is currently considered solved after thermal simulations, whose results, approximate and based on various assumptions and scenarios [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16], are now challenged by the simpler, direct and precise result presented in Sect. 3.1, which *exactly corresponds to the acceleration of $-8.74 \times 10^{-10} \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ measured by the NASA*. The modified Stokes's formula, put into Newton's second law of motion, says that due to the large masses of planets (unlike the case of the Pioneer probes), planetary orbits are stable over billions of years, averting what would be otherwise a major objection to the existence of a shear-thickening vacuum, i.e. its effect on orbital stability. Sect. 3.3 shows that vacuum's apparent (shear-dependent) viscosity emerges as the real cause of the anomalous precession of perihelia, suggesting that the quantum foundations of relativity are based on a fluid, shear-thickening quantum vacuum. In fact, it is shown that Einstein's formula for the precession of perihelia can be directly derived from the modified Stokes's formula. The conclusion also suggests possible reasons for vacuum dilatancy, building a bridge to the dark sector and to the Higgs field, while further research in this direction is expected.

2 Methods: modified Stokes's law for a dilatant vacuum

Stokes' law, derived in 1851, to calculate the viscous force acting on a body traveling through a viscous, Newtonian fluid [18], reads

$$F_v = -6\pi r v \eta \quad (1)$$

where v is the translational velocity, r the radius of the object (the law refers to spherical shape) and η is a coefficient of dynamic viscosity expressed in $\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$. However, for a shear-thickening vacuum, the viscosity coefficient η , in Eq. (1), is not appropriate, since it is valid only for Newtonian fluids. To express a dilatant vacuum, we need a nonlinear law. In the present investigation it is demonstrated (Sect. 3) that the correct mathematical behavior of shear stress

for the physical vacuum is expressed by the Lorentz factor, therefore reinterpreted as vacuum's rheogram, in which the asymptote at the speed of light consequently refers to a transient, solid-like condition of the vacuum, which occurs when approaching a certain level of shear stress. Let us then replace η with the Lorentz factor, using the expression $\gamma - 1$, which also expresses the speed v of Eq. (1). We arrive to a modified Stokes's equation

$$F_{vac} = -6\pi r(\gamma - 1)\kappa = -6\pi r \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) \kappa \quad (2)$$

where κ is a unitary constant expressed in $\text{Kg} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$. Let us also define

$$D = \gamma - 1 \quad (3)$$

as a dimensionless term of vacuum dilatancy. The formula is simply written $F_{vac} = -6\pi r D \kappa$. If we use this formula for bodies traveling in a vacuum, such as probes or planets, the viscous force it refers to is of course that of the physical vacuum, so Eq. (2) is the formula for the viscous force exerted by a dilatant vacuum: and its applications and validity are presented in the following sections, by precisely solving – as announced – two known anomalies and by obtaining other correct results, such as the stability of planetary orbits.

3 Results: shear-thickening vacuum proven

3.1 Exact value for the Pioneer acceleration

Being the anomalous negative acceleration of the Pioneer spacecrafts 10 and 11 well-known (concrete investigations of that anomaly started in 1994 [12]), it is not necessary to summarize here this issue. In the light of the exact result presented below, it appears evident that this problem has not been correctly solved yet, despite copious investigations, based on thermal simulations [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16], which produced approximate results from several assumptions and different scenarios. In 2012 [10] a value of $7.4(\pm 2.5) \times 10^{-10} \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ was

proposed. On the contrary, the exact solution (without models and assumptions) is directly offered by Eq. (2), that is, via the interaction of the Pioneer probes with a shear-thickening vacuum. Let us put Eq. (2) in Newton’s second law, using the known data of the Pioneer probes and *we directly obtain the exact negative acceleration of the Pioneer (a_P) detected by the NASA*

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_P = \frac{F_{vac}}{m_P} &= -\frac{6\pi r_P \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v_{max}}{c}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) \kappa}{m_P} = \\
 &= -\frac{6\pi \cdot 1.371 \text{ m} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{36737 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}}{299792458 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) \cdot 1 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}}{222 \text{ kg}} = \\
 &= -8.74 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where $m_P = 222 \text{ kg}$ is the mass of the spacecrafts (258 kg) minus that of the burned fuel (36 kg hydrazine) after the Jupiter flyby; $r_P = 1.371 \text{ m}$ is the radius of the antenna (diameter is 9 ft) and $v_{max} = 36737 \text{ m/s}$ is the maximum speed of the probe, as indicated by the NASA’s Scientific and Technical Information Office [17] after the swing-by caused by Jupiter. This exact and direct result cannot be ignored and the Pioneer issue has to be reopened. Moreover, the NASA should now consider to Doppler track other probes. Unfortunately this was not the case of the New Horizons spacecraft, for which data are missing. Testing other probes (maybe a dedicated probe) with Eq.(2) would be definitely useful.

3.2 Second test: Stability of planetary orbits

The existence of a shear-thickening vacuum does immediately arise an objection as regards orbital stability. However, considering the second law of motion in the form $a = F/m$ and putting the large mass of a planet in the denominator and the modified Stokes’s equation in the numerator, we see that, despite the existence of a dilatant vacuum, planetary orbits are stable over trillions of years. For instance, the deceleration of the Earth (a_{\oplus}) corresponds to the

following negligible value

$$a_{\oplus} = \frac{F_{vac}}{m_{\oplus}} = - \frac{6\pi(6371000 \text{ m}) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{29780 \text{ m/s}}{299792458 \text{ m/s}} \right)^2}} - 1 \right) \cdot 1 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}}{5.97 \times 10^{24} \text{ kg}} = -9.92 \times 10^{-26} \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2} \quad (5)$$

using in the numerator Eq. (2) with mean radius and mean orbital velocity of the Earth and the mass of the Earth in the denominator. Subscript \oplus refers to the Earth. Such a negative acceleration corresponds to a decrease in orbital speed $< -3.13 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m/s}$ per billion years, making orbits stable for thousands billions years. For Jupiter, orbital deceleration is $-6.59 \times 10^{-28} \text{ m/s}^2$. One therefore concludes that planetary orbits are stable despite the presence of a shear-thickening vacuum.

3.3 Deriving Einstein's formula for the precession of perihelia

Net of classical gravitational contributions, perihelia precessions show an anomalous positive contribution, which is particularly evident for the planet Mercury. The correct calculation of this anomaly is one of the classical tests for general relativity (GR). Here Einstein's formula for the precession of perihelia is differently derived via the modified Stokes's equation presented above. In this way, it is suggested that the long-awaited quantum foundations of general relativity are situated in a shear-thickening quantum vacuum. In GR [19], the anomalous perihelia precession is represented by a formula which can be observed in three equivalent forms

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{24\pi^3 a^2}{T^2(1-e^2)c^2} = 6\pi \left(\frac{v}{c} \right)^2 \frac{1}{1-e^2} = 6\pi \frac{GM}{a(1-e^2)c^2} \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta\phi$ expresses the relativistic contribution to perihelia precessions in radians per revolution corresponding, using the data of Mercury, to the known value of $42.98''$ per century (or $5.0186 \times 10^{-7} \text{ rad/rev.}$), $a = r$ is the semi-major axis, T the orbital period and $e = 0.205$ the orbital

eccentricity. The expression in the center of Eq. (6) is obtained via the equivalence $T^2 = 4\pi^2 a^2/v^2$, resorting to mean orbital velocity, and in the expression on the right the stable second cosmic velocity, $v = \sqrt{GM/r}$, is used. As for the case of the Pioneer, the modified Stokes's equation for a dilatant vacuum is used below. In this case, the treatment of the planet as a point mass is respected, as in GR, so the direct proportionality to planetary radius is not taken into account and by resorting to the dimensionless norm of Eq. (2) we obtain

$$6\pi \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) = 6\pi (\gamma - 1) \quad (7)$$

which can be expressed in radians. Resorting to Taylor, let us proceed via the approximation

$$2(\gamma - 1) \approx \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2 \quad (8)$$

and Eq. (7) now reads

$$3\pi \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2 = 3\pi \frac{GM}{ac^2} \quad (9)$$

where, on the right, we see again the stable second cosmic velocity (here squared), as in the rightmost expression in Eq. (6). Since we are considering an elliptic orbit, we have to use the elliptic parameter, correcting a into $a(1 - e^2)$ and we obtain a formula which exactly gives 1/2 the result of GR (6)

$$\Delta\phi = 3\pi \frac{GM}{a(1 - e^2)c^2} = 3\pi \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2 \frac{1}{1 - e^2} \quad (10)$$

This 1/2 result can be considered as the precession *occurring in a semi-orbit* and is due to the use of mean orbital velocity. Indeed, in the elliptic orbit, the orbital speed actually varies as in Fig. 1 on the left side. Since the mean orbital velocity is given as $(v_{max}/2) + (v_{min}/2)$, let us adopt the reduced model on the right side of Fig. 1, i.e. one semi-orbit at maximum orbital speed and one at minimum speed. The full precession (6) is therefore given by

$$\Delta\phi = 3\pi \left(\frac{v_{max}}{c}\right)^2 \frac{1}{1 - e^2} + 3\pi \left(\frac{v_{min}}{c}\right)^2 \frac{1}{1 - e^2} = 6\pi \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2 \frac{1}{1 - e^2} = \frac{24\pi^3 a^2}{T^2(1 - e^2)c^2} \quad (11)$$

Figure 1: Left: variable orbital velocity in the elliptic orbit (P and A refer to perihelion and aphelion, respectively). Right: the reduced model used in the present study, which considers half an orbit at maximum orbital velocity and the other one at minimum velocity.

where v_{max} and v_{min} , each referring to a semi-orbit, recombine in the mean orbital velocity v and the rightmost equivalence comes from Eq. (6). Now, by merging the steps above in a single formula, we can look at the relationship between the modified Stokes's equation, which expresses the viscous force in a dilatant vacuum, and the contribution to the precession of perihelia. The formula reads

$$\Delta\phi \equiv \left\| \frac{2F_{vac}}{\kappa r(1-e^2)} \right\| = 12\pi \frac{D}{(1-e^2)} \quad (12)$$

where D is the term of vacuum dilatancy (3). By testing Eq. (12) with the parameters of the planet Mercury, we see that *it exactly gives the well-known value of general relativity*

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\phi &= 12\pi \frac{D}{(1-e^2)} = 12\pi \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{GM}{ac^2}\right)}-1} \right)}{(1-e^2)} = \\ &= 12\pi \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{(6.67408 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-2})(1.98847 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg})}{(5.7909 \times 10^{10} \text{ m})(299792458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1})^2}}-1} \right)}{1-0.20563^2} \right)}{=} \\ &= 5.018649 \times 10^{-7} \text{ rad/rev.} \Rightarrow 42.98''/\text{century} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where, in D , $v = \sqrt{GM/a}$ is used, as in Eq. (6). The positive contribution to the precession of perihelia treated in general relativity is in this way revealed as a phenomenon driven by

a shear-thickening vacuum. We see that nothing, in the present study, contradicts general relativity: this investigation, by rederiving Einstein's formula for perihelia precession, only highlights that the quantum foundations of relativity are in a dilatant quantum vacuum, as Eq. (12) shows. After all, this is compatible with the stress-energy tensor of the field equation, in which T^{00} is vacuum's energy/mass density (ρ_{vac}), also present in the cosmological constant $\Lambda = \kappa\rho_{vac}$, and the remaining components of the tensor can be as well hydrodynamically interpreted, being pressure, shear stress, momentum flux and momentum density. Interestingly, also an investigation by Conti and Marcucci [20], following the present findings [21], shows that the interaction at Planck-scale with a quantum fluid may be cause of precession.

4 Conclusion

The modification of Stokes's law, obtained by replacing η with the Lorentz factor (in the form $\gamma - 1$), reinterpreted as the rheogram of a fluid, shear-thickening vacuum, has produced a new formula expressing the viscous force exerted by physical vacuum. This formula has been confirmed by solving two well-known anomalies, the relativistic contribution to perihelia precession, rederiving Einstein's equation, and the Pioneer anomaly, for which a direct and exact result has been obtained, to be therefore preferred to the more approximate and complicate solutions sofar presented. Deriving Einstein's formula for the precession of perihelia from the viscous force of physical vacuum suggests that the quantum foundations of relativity are rooted in the existence of a shear-thickening quantum vacuum. We can conclude by considering that such a vacuum may correspond to the dark sector, i.e. to 95% of the universe's mass-energy, in which diffused dark matter particles (a granular component) could play the role of a dopant in a sea of superfluid dark energy, determining vacuum dilatancy. Nevertheless, also the Higgs field, as an ubiquitous, scalar, viscous field, could be the reason for the existence of a dilatant vacuum. For sure, the shear-thickening aspect of the physical vacuum helps us to better understand

its nature, along perhaps with that of dark energy and dark matter, soliciting further specific research.

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